

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

ABCB9 functions in multi-drug resistance in human cancer.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We describe here a function for the ATP-binding cassette gene *ABCB6* in multi-drug resistance in human cancer (1-3), supported by evidence by demonstrating its transcriptional up-regulation with significance at the transcriptome level in metastasis to distant organ sites in human breast cancer (4, 5), and by separate evidence demonstrating that ATP-binding cassette genes function in multi-drug resistance: in resistance to a platinum agent, in resistance to doxorubicin, and in resistance to paclitaxel (2).

Results

Figure 1: ABCB9 is differentially expressed in the brain metastases of humans with breast cancer.

I. Metastasis to the brain in humans with breast cancer.

n=8 primary tumor of the breast (human)

n=5 metastasis to the brain (human)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
23457	4.98E-02	0.3868	-1.9613276	-0.75867015	531.38	ABCB9	7236/21403	66.2

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors in humans with breast cancer and metastasis to the brain, we discovered differential expression of endothelial cell adhesion molecule, encoded by *ABCB9* in metastasis to the brain in breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of *ABCB9* changed more than 65% of the human breast cancer transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 21,403 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *ABCB9* messenger RNA in breast cancer brain metastasis, demonstrating up-regulation of *ABCB9* during disease progression and metastasis.

Discussion

We described here transcriptional induction of a gene with functions in multi-drug resistance, in brain metastasis in human breast cancer. Novel approaches to challenging metastasis and resistance will utilize chemotherapy in conjunction with i) kinase and phosphatase inhibitors targeted to tissue and tumor type whose functions overlap with that of growth factor and growth factor receptor inhibitors, ii) inhibitors of the ATP-binding cassette family (multi-drug resistance pumps), and iii) CDK4/6 inhibitors, which function as senescence-inducing agents.

1 **References**

- 2 1. Gottesman, M.M., Fojo, T. and Bates, S.E., 2002. Multidrug resistance in cancer: role of
3 ATP-dependent transporters. *Nature reviews cancer*, 2(1), pp.48-58.
- 4 2. Mamoor, S. 2025. ATP-binding cassette genes function in multi-drug resistance in human cancer.
- 5 3. Robey, R.W., Pluchino, K.M., Hall, M.D., Fojo, A.T., Bates, S.E. and Gottesman, M.M., 2018.
6 Revisiting the role of ABC transporters in multidrug-resistant cancer. *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 18(7),
pp.452-464.
- 7 4. GSE191230: Ong, L.T., Lee, W.C., Ma, S., Oguz, G., Niu, Z., Bao, Y., Yusuf, M., Lee, P.L., Goh,
8 J.Y., Wang, P. and Yong, K.S.M., 2022. IFI16-dependent STING signaling is a crucial regulator of
anti-HER2 immune response in HER2+ breast cancer. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*,
119(31), p.e2201376119.
- 9 5. GSE10893: Weigman, V.J., Chao, H.H., Shabalin, A.A., He, X., Parker, J.S., Nordgard, S.H.,
10 Grushko, T., Huo, D., Nwachukwu, C., Nobel, A. and Kristensen, V.N., 2012. Basal-like Breast cancer
DNA copy number losses identify genes involved in genomic instability, response to therapy, and patient
11 survival. *Breast cancer research and treatment*, 133, pp.865-880.
- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15
- 16
- 17
- 18
- 19
- 20
- 21
- 22
- 23
- 24
- 25
- 26
- 27
- 28

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We measured total transcription in primary tumors and metastasis to distant organ sites including the bones, the brain, the liver and the lungs using microarray and RNA-sequencing datasets (GSEXXXXX and GSEXXXXX) and R-based computational software for exact quantitative determination of multi-drug resistant pump transcriptional induction at the transcriptome level.